

1 **A transcript whose expression distinguishes lipopolysaccharide and muramyl dipeptide**
2 **recognition.**

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7 The innate immune system distinguishes between self and non-self by detecting and responding to
8 biochemicals that correspond to foreign structures. Whether pattern recognition receptors that respond to
9 overlapping or shared structures from the same insult (pathogen) are able to produce unique effectors
10 during the rapid innate immune response is incompletely understood. We measured total transcription in
11 the whole blood, in monocytes and in macrophages following exposure to pathogen associated molecular
12 patterns from the gram negative bacterial cell wall: lipopolysaccharide, recognized by the toll-like receptor
13 TLR4 or muramyl dipeptide, recognized by the NLR family sensor NOD2. We identified the alpha subunit
14 of the interleukin-27 receptor IL27R as a transcript produced uniquely in response to muramyl dipeptide
15 signaling. Specificity of IL27R as an MDP-induced effector was supported by systems biologic analysis
16 that demonstrated NOD2 but not TLR4 was closely co-regulated with IL27RA. Innate immune sensors
17 that detect gram-negative molecular patterns produce largely shared and overlapping transcriptional
18 responses, but aspects of discrete, MDP-specific responses by NOD2 and LPS- specific responses by
19 TLR4 do exist.
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